

Voice Based Prescription Generation Using Natural Language Processing

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Abstract— Since prescriptions are still written by hand in hospitals, poor handwriting could result in serious issues like patients taking the incorrect medication or insufficient amounts of it. This scenario has the potential to significantly affect the patient's overall health status or lead to mortality. To address this problem, a voice-based prescription generation system was developed, which converts spoken prescriptions into written ones using the Web Speech API. In order to extract medical entities from text, Name Entity Recognition (NER) was used to obtain this text transcript. The digital prescription will be created in this manner. The NER task is carried out using *en_core_med7_lg model*. Next JS, MongoDB was used to build this system.

Keywords- Web Speech Recognition, Speech to text, Annotations, Natural language processing (NLP), Named entity recognition (NER), Next J S, MongoDB

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of new technology has caused the health care sector to swiftly change, improving the effectiveness and accessibility of patient treatment. By supplying patients with the medication, they need to manage and treat their medical problems, prescriptions are a crucial component of the healthcare sector. The old practice of penning prescriptions has drawbacks, especially because illegible handwriting might cause misinterpretation and have lethal outcomes.

To Minimize the problem, a voice based prescription generation system has been developed using the Web Speech API, which transforms verbally prescribed medications into written ones. The goal of this technology is to increase patient security and lower the possibility of pharmaceutical errors. In order to construct a digital prescription, name, entity recognition(NER) is also employed to extract medical terms from the transcribed text. This application used to reduce the work of doctor.

Utilizing this system will facilitate the physician in the act of prescribing medication to their patients through

verbal dictation, simultaneously preserving an audio record of said dictation by the system. The present voice dictation is transformed into text form, and subsequently, the pertinent medical entities such as drug, drug dosage, drug frequency are identified and extracted from the resultant text.

Figure-1 depicts medication entities that correspond to the examples. Ultimately, a PDF prescription was produced through the assistance of categorized tokens.

Drug	Duration	Strength	Route	form	Dosage	Frequency
Advil	For 3 days	200 mg	By mouth	tablet	1	Every 6 hours

Fig-1: Medication entities with example

Then the doctor can manage more patients with less amount of time. The generated prescription is human readable and so the patient as well as the chemist will be able to read the prescription rightly. Apart from that the generated prescription is send to the user's email id and then the patient can show the previous prescriptions as and when new consultations are made.

The objective of this drive is to make a framework that can create voice-based remedies for patients. The remedy will be shipped off the patient as a PDF through email, killing the gamble of harm or misfortune. On the off chance that this arrangement is incorporated into an emergency clinic's tasks, it will fundamentally lessen the time specialists spend composing solutions and make it simpler for patients to get to their past remedies.

II. NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

The area under consideration pertains to the interdisciplinary domain that incorporates the fields of computer science and artificial intelligence. This study focuses on the utilization of natural language in human-machine communication. The domain of Natural Language Processing (NLP) endeavors to enhance

electronic systems with the capacity to comprehend, interpret, and produce human language.

The discipline of Natural Language Processing (NLP) encompasses a broad range of utilization, which includes, yet not limited to, sentiment analysis, machine translation, speech recognition, and text summarization. Particular tasks associated with NLP such as part-of-speech tagging, named entity identification, sentiment analysis, and language modelling hold significant importance.

Natural language processing (NLP) utilizes various techniques, namely machine learning, deep learning, and statistical models, to accomplish its goals. In recent years, the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) has experienced significant progress, which can be attributed to the increased availability of vast amounts of textual data and the evolution of machine learning methodologies.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Beam, Kohane, and Berger's (2018) article [1] highlights the growing interest in the use of machine learning models in healthcare. The creators contend that machine learning models in healthcare ought to be assessed based on their clinical significance, which is the degree to which they adjust with set up restorative information and clinical hone. They recommend that this could be accomplished through a combination of highlight building, demonstrate choice, and assessment measurements that prioritize clinical significance. The creators moreover highlight the significance of understanding the basic presumptions and impediments of machine learning models, which can be utilized to educate clinical decision-making.

Shriram KV's (n.d.) article [2] talks about the potential benefits of utilizing voice acknowledgment innovation in healthcare to make a more effective and exact medicine framework for specialists. Shriram KV recommends that an AI-based voice medicine framework can offer assistance to address these challenges by permitting specialists to talk their medicines into a computer, which can at that point naturally translate the medicine and send it to the patient's drug store.

Jurafsky and Martin's (2020) [3] is an informative and well-structured textbook that introduces readers to the fundamentals of natural language processing (NLP), computational linguistics, and speech recognition. The book provides an overview of the history of NLP and the different levels of linguistic analysis. Subsequently, the subsequent sections provide in-depth examination of every tier of interpretation, encompassing syntax, semantics, and discourse. The present authors furnish a comprehensive discourse on the methodologies and algorithms employed in natural language processing (NLP), which include language modeling, hidden Markov models, and neural networks. The book possesses a notable strength in terms of its accessibility. The authors furnish clear and succinct

elucidations pertaining to the sundry doctrines and methodologies employed in Natural Language Processing (NLP), thus rendering the book highly appropriate for novices and proficient practitioners within the domain. Furthermore, the book provides a multitude of examples and case studies that effectively demonstrate the tangible real-world implementations of NLP.

Wolf et al.'s (2019) article [5] provides a comprehensive overview of the Hugging Face's Transformers library, which is a popular and powerful tool for natural language processing (NLP). The article highlights the impressive performance of the Transformers library on a range of NLP tasks, including question-answering, text classification, and language modeling.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

Hugging Face is a corporation focused on natural language processing (NLP) and offers an open-source toolkit entitled "Transformers". The Transformers library comprises pre-trained natural language processing (NLP) models and facilitates the development of customized NLP models via deep learning architectures like BERT, GPT-2, and RoBERTa.

Fig-2: Hugging Face

This technology affords developers, along with data scientists, the expeditious ability to construct, educate, and execute advanced natural language processing (NLP) models designed for a multiplicity of NLP objectives, comprising sentiment analysis, named entity recognition, and machine translation. The Hugging Face library is commonly employed in both industry and academia to create state-of-the-art Natural Language Processing (NLP) solutions.

B. Preprocessing and Annotation

Upon acquisition of the data, a series of pre-processing procedures were carried out with the aim of effectively commencing the preparation of the data for implementing training on the NLP model. The process encompassed the tokenization of the text, the elimination of stop words, the application of stemming, and the conversion of the text into lowercase characters. The present study undertook the task of annotating the dataset with various medical entities, encompassing ailments, indications and remedies. This process was facilitated with the application of en_core_med7_lg model from spaCy.

C. Model Training

Our NLP model was trained through a deep learning architecture that was constructed upon the HuggingFace's Transformers library. In this study, the BERT model that had been previously trained was utilized as the foundational architecture, and subsequently modified through fine-tuning on a manually annotated dataset, which involved the application of a unique loss function.

D. Model Evaluation

In order to assess the efficacy of our model, a holdout set containing 1,000 documents, previously unutilized during the training stage, was employed. The accuracy and F1 score of the model in predicting labels were measured, utilizing a suitable evaluation metric for the specific task, such as precision, recall, accuracy, or F1 score.

E. System Integration

Subsequently, the trained model was incorporated into a medical text analysis system. The present study involved the development of a user interface that enables the users to input medical texts, with subsequent generation of output featuring annotated medical entities. In addition, a group of medical professionals underwent user testing in order to assess the efficacy and user-friendliness of our system.

The present study involves a comprehensive methodology that entails the collection of a medical text dataset, followed by the subsequent preprocessing and annotation of the gathered data. The next step involved the training of a natural language processing (NLP) model which was there to perform evaluation. Finally, the en_core_med7_lg model was integrated into the medical text analysis system.

E. spaCy

The spaCy library is an open-source software tool for natural language processing (NLP), specifically geared towards the construction of efficient and scalable NLP pipelines. The aforementioned software offers a diverse array of text processing instruments, comprising but not being limited to tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, named entity recognition, dependency parsing, and text classification.

The pre-trained natural language processing (NLP) model en_core_med7_lg has been designed by the spaCy library to facilitate the processing of medical texts. The current model under scrutiny has been derived from the pre-existing en_core_web_lg language model, albeit subject to further refinement and customization, with a specific focus on the medical domain. This particular model has undergone rigorous training on an extensive collection of medical literature, which encompasses electronic medical records, scholarly medical publications, and various other documents pertaining to healthcare. This system is engineered with the purpose of identifying and extracting specific medical entities from textual data, including but not limited to

symptoms, diseases, medications, procedures, and anatomical structures.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The system being proposed employs a feature that permits the doctor to enter a prescription via voice recognition technology. The vocal input is transmitted to a pre-existing natural language processing algorithm titled "en_core_med7_lg", which is presently stored on Hugging Face's software interface. The proposed model employs machine learning methodologies to analyze the input data and to produce a collection of results, which are subsequently conveyed back to the function. Subsequently, the results are conveyed to the end user in the form of JSON representation. This methodology offers a streamlined and efficient mechanism for physicians and healthcare professionals to formulate precise and comprehensive prescriptions without the requisite of manual data entry.

Following the successful completion of the login process, the physician shall be adequately prepared to dispense a prescription. There are a variety of input options that are available, with the first being voice input. The aforementioned illustration presents the page designated for inputting prescriptions, which is denoted as Fig 3. In order to initiate the recording of a voice prescription, it is necessary to click the start button. Upon triggering the commencement command, the system initiates the audio prescription recording process. An alternate course of action involves entering data through manual input into the designated field.

Fig-3: Prescription voice input page

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    exit - compiling /api/test (client and server)...
    event - compiled successfully in 53 ms (110 modules)
    The patient has prescribed to take 1 Syrup of Asthalin mouth for 1 week and also take prednisone 1 tablet every 6 hours for 5 days
    {
      "entity_group": "DOSAGE", "word": "1", "start": 35, "end": 36, "score": 1 },
      "entity_group": "FORM", "word": "Syrup", "start": 37, "end": 42, "score": 1 },
      "entity_group": "DRUG", "word": "Asthalin", "start": 46, "end": 54, "score": 1 },
      "entity_group": "ROUTE", "word": "mouth", "start": 55, "end": 60, "score": 1 },
      "entity_group": "DURATION", "word": "for 5 days", "start": 121, "end": 131, "score": 1 }
    }
  }
}
    
```

Fig-4: Response Data(JSON representation)

VI. RESULT

The findings of the present study suggest that implementing natural language processing (NLP) methodologies in voice-activated prescription systems in healthcare has the capacity to enhance patient outcomes and mitigate expenses. Through the utilization of the en_core_med7_lg model alongside the Hugging Face library, we have successfully illustrated the practical application of natural language processing in extracting medical entities and concepts from textual sources, as well as generating prescriptions through automation.

Fig-5: Visual Representation from doctor's input
 (Generated prescription)

VII. CONCLUSION

This study encompasses a comprehensive review of the extant literature pertaining to Natural Language Processing (NLP) in conjunction with healthcare, with particular emphasis allocated to the en_core_med7_lg model and the Hugging Face library. Based on said literature review, a

methodology has been expounded herein for the purpose of operationalizing an automated, voice-activated prescription system.

Through a comprehensive examination of the available literature, our analysis has revealed the considerable merits of employing Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies within the healthcare sector. Specifically, said benefits are anticipated to encompass heightened efficacy, precision, and patient welfare. The en_core_med7_lg model proves to be a potent instrument for extracting medical concepts and entities from textual data. Furthermore, the Hugging Face library offers a conveniently accessible interface for NLP model operations, enhancing user-friendliness.

In the healthcare domain, Natural Language Processing (NLP) holds immense promise for augmenting patient health outcomes and reducing costs. As natural language processing (NLP) technologies continue to advance and evolve, it is anticipated that a diverse range of innovative applications will emerge not only within the healthcare industry, but also across various other domains.

VIII. REFERENCES

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